

PID: 36485-Nikolina Novakov-New common carp technology for new climate era

Version 1

Description

The DMP will cover several aspects, starting from data collection and who is responsible for which type of data, through the type and size of data to be collected and which will be divided into three sections, or three data work packages: The first group will contain data related to water quality parameters (ammonium-nitrogen, total ammonia, nitrite-nitrogen, nitrate-nitrogen, total phosphorus, biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), temperature, oxygen and pH content and data on zooplankton and phytoplankton abundance. The second group will contain data on fish production performance. The third group will contain data on health and stress analysis of fish. After collecting raw data, they will be statistically processed, prepared for publication and deposited in the open data repository, as primary and processed data.

Funder

Grant

Researchers

Nikolina Novakov (0000-0002-3951-4282), Jelena Stanivuk (0009-0001-5939-5284), Uros Ljubobratovic (0000-0002-1972-467X)

Organizations

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Research Institute
for Fisheries and Aquaculture

1. Main Info

Title of Plan: [PID: 36485-Nikolina Novakov-New common carp technology for new climate era](#)

Description:

The DMP will cover several aspects, starting from data collection and who is responsible for which type of data, through the type and size of data to be collected and which will be divided into three sections, or three data work packages: The first group will contain data related to water quality parameters (ammonium-nitrogen, total ammonia, nitrite-nitrogen, nitrate-nitrogen, total phosphorus, biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), temperature, oxygen and pH content and data on zooplankton and phytoplankton abundance. The second group will contain data on fish production performance. The third group will contain data on health and stress analysis of fish. After collecting raw data, they will be statistically processed, prepared for publication and deposited in the open data repository, as primary and processed data.

Researchers:

[Nikolina Novakov \(0000-0002-3951-4282\)](#)

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[Uros Ljubobratovic \(0000-0002-1972-467X\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture](#)

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Access: [Public](#)

2. Ethics

Introduction:

All procedures involving fish will be conducted in line with the Hungarian legislation on experimental animals and are approved by the National Scientific Ethical Committee on Animal Experimentation.

The health status of fishes will be monitored daily by checking the pond, and during the probe harvesting every three weeks. In the case of disease outbreak, fish in all investigated ponds will be treated according to diagnosis and national veterinary legislation. The stress parameters of the fish will be regularly checked, and the obvious response (appetite, aquatic surface respiration) of fish to stress conditions will be constantly monitored. Fish blood for stress parameters would be taken from the same fish that are being examined for health checks. Should the stress levels increased to unacceptable level, the ponds would be refilled with water to the initial level. All effort will be made to minimize the fish's suffering. For that reason, the fish will be anesthetized using MS-222. Only the minimum required number of fish will be used during the experiment (6 fish from each facility for 5 times check).

3. Dataset descriptions

Introduction:

1. Data Summary

1.1. Data Summary

1.1.1. Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

1.1.2. What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Clear Class

1.1.3.What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Clear Class

1.1.4.What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

Clear Class

1.1.5.What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Clear Class

1.1.6.To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Clear Class

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1.Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.1.2.Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

No

Metadata

Metadata

List of values provided by external source(s)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Clear Class

Please specify

2.1.3. Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.1.4. Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.2. Making data accessible

2.2.1. Repository

2.2.1.1. Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.2.1.2. Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.2.1.3. Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.2.2. Data

2.2.2.1. Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.2.2.2. If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Clear Class

2.2.2.3. Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.2.2.4. If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Clear Class

Please specify data access process

2.2.2.5.How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

H1 header

Please specify security provisions

2.2.2.6.Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.2.3. Metadata

2.2.3.1.Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes

No

2.2.3.2.How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Clear Class

2.2.3.3.Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.3. Making data interoperable

2.3.1. What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Clear Class

2.3.2. In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Clear Class

2.3.3. Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.4. Increase data re-use

2.4.1.How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Please select

Clear Class

Please specify

2.4.2.Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Yes

No

Select license(s)

Select license(s)

List of values provided by external source(s)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Clear Class

Please specify

2.4.3.Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.4.4. Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

2.4.5. Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Clear Class

3. Data security

3.1. Data security

3.1.1. What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Clear Class

3.1.2. Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4. Other research outputs

4.1. Making other research outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

4.1.1. Will other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.1.2. Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

No

Metadata

Metadata

List of values provided by external source(s)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Clear Class

Please specify

4.1.3. Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.1.4. Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.2. Making other research outputs accessible

4.2.1. Repository

4.2.1.1. Will the other research outputs be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.2.1.2. Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your other research outputs will be deposited?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.2.1.3. Does the repository ensure that the other research outputs is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.2.2. Other research outputs

4.2.2.1. Will all other research outputs be made openly available? If certain research outputs cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their research outputs closed if opening their research outputs goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.2.2.2.If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research outputs should be made available as soon as possible.

Clear Class

4.2.2.3.Will the other research outputs be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.2.2.4.If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the other research outputs, both during and after the end of the project?

Clear Class

Please specify other research outputs access process

4.2.2.5.How will the identity of the person accessing the other research outputs be ascertained?

Clear Class

Please specify security provisions

4.2.2.6. Is there a need for an other research output access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive other research output)?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.2.3. Metadata

4.2.3.1. Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the other research outputs?

Yes

No

4.2.3.2. How long will the other research outputs remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after other research outputs is no longer available?

Clear Class

4.2.3.3. Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the other research outputs be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.3. Making other research outputs interoperable

4.3.1. What other research outputs and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your other research outputs interoperable to allow other research outputs exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Clear Class

4.3.2. In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Clear Class

4.3.3. Will your other research outputs include qualified references to other research outputs (e.g. other research outputs from your project, or other research outputs from previous research)?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.4. Increase other research outputs re-use

4.4.1. How will you provide documentation needed to validate other research outputs analysis and facilitate other research outputs re-use (e.g. readme files with information on

methodology, codebooks, research outputs cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Please select

Clear Class

Please specify

4.4.2. Will your other research outputs be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your other research outputs be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Yes

No

Select license(s)

Select license(s)

List of values provided by external source(s)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Clear Class

Please specify

4.4.3. Will the other research outputs produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.4.4. Will the provenance of the other research outputs be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

4.4.5. Describe all relevant other research outputs quality assurance processes.

Clear Class

4.4.6. Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, research outputs security and ethical aspects.

Clear Class

5. Allocation of resources

5.1. Allocation of resources

5.1.1. What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Direct cost

Indirect cost

Select activity

5.1.2.How will these be covered?

Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

Clear Class

5.1.3.Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Select researchers

Select researchers

List of values provided by external source(s)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Clear Class

Please specify

5.1.4.How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Name of resource / activity Description Value Currency

6. Ethics

6.1. Ethics

6.1.1.Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

6.1.2. Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes

No

Clear Class

Please specify

7. Other issues

7.1. Other issues

7.1.1. Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Yes

No

Descriptions

[AQUASERV | all categories | generic template](#)

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divided into three sections, or three data work packages: The first group will contain data related to water quality parameters (ammonium-nitrogen, total ammonia, nitrite-nitrogen, nitrate-nitrogen, total phosphorus, biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), temperature, oxygen and pH content and data on zooplankton and phytoplankton abundance. The second group will contain data on fish production performance. The third group will contain data on health and stress analysis of fish. After collecting raw data, they will be statistically processed, prepared for publication and deposited in the open data repository, as primary and processed data.

Template: [AQUASERV](#) | [all categories](#) | [generic template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

No

We will primarily use the data and publish an Open Access publication. Through it, it will be possible to cite the obtained research results.

1.1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Structured data will be generated, easily searchable and stored in tabular formats (rows and columns):

Water quality data will be numerically quantitative;

Fish production performance data will also be numerically and quantitative;

Fish health data will be qualitative, and fish stress data will be continuous numerically.

1.1.3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose is that the generated and later statistically processed data serve for an easier estimate of the impact of daily aeration on oxygen concentration, and other physical, chemical, and biological water parameters compared on 1 m and 1.7 m of water depth setups, evaluating its effect and applicability for intensive culture. The effects of applying these technologies would be assessed by evaluating fish survival, individual growth, feed conversion, health status and welfare.

1.1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The expected data size would include tables that would not exceed 500 KB.

1.1.5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Data is generated based on original measurements during the experiment.

1.1.6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

To scientists and common carp producers, in order to optimize and improve the technology by applying some of the researched factors and outcomes. Since intensive carp production has the ultimate goal of producing market-ready carp within one growing season, these outcomes would be applicable to achieving this ultimate goal. Finally, the obtained data and results can help producers to adapt production technology to new climatic conditions.

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

Yes. It will be identified by a permanent identifier, which in our case will be obtained values that are not variable.

2.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

Metadata will be provided to allow discovery and will be published in the paper. The following metadata will be created: numerically quantitative, shown in exact values related to water quality parameters; numerically and quantitative, related to the values of carp production performance;

qualitative, which describe the health status of the fish and the presence of certain pathogens; and continuous numerical, which are related to the stress state of the fish.

Standards will be used according to the manufacturer's instructions. For example, when measuring glucose and cortisol levels in fish, these methods are standardized by the manufacturers of the ELISA or other diagnostic kits themselves. Diagnostic methods will be carried out according to ISO diagnostic standards or according to literature references and keys for the identification of individual parasites. Water quality measurements will also be carried out according to internationally standardized methodology and production performances such as length and weight using classical standard measuring instruments.

2.1.3 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Keywords will be set according to the keywords in the manuscript and will depend on the data itself.

2.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

Yes, it will be in a database from which it can be harvested.

2.2 Making data accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

In the repository of the University of Novi Sad.

2.2.1.2 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

It is a repository of institution at University of Novi Sad. In accordance with Serbian law, every scientific institution must have its own digital repository. As a person employed at the University, a special Agreement is not required.

2.2.1.3 Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Provides, and assigns a link as an identifier from which data can be harvested.

2.2.2 Data

2.2.2.1 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

All data will be openly available.

2.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

They will be available as soon as all measurements are completed.

2.2.2.3 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Data will be accessible through a free access protocol.

2.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

There are no restrictions on use that would prevent access to data.

2.2.2.5 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

The data will be available via the link where it was deposited.

2.2.3 Metadata

2.2.3.1 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

No

Metadata will be displayed in the published manuscript and will contain information to enable the user to access the original data.

2.2.3.2 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

The institutional repository is a permanent database so they will be stored there for a long time. Metadata will be included in published manuscript and permanently available.

2.2.3.3 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

The data will be on the repository link in the form of excel or pdf documents.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

The data is interoperable and can be easily interpreted by interested parties from other disciplines because it is numerical, quantitative or qualitatively descriptive and clearly provides a representation of certain parameters. Numerical values are expressed in standard units.

2.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

We don't have vague parameters that need to be mapped and explained in more detail.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Units of measurement

All methodological parameters that were used to obtain data will be presented and shown in the published manuscript, in such a way that they can be repeated.

2.4.2 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

They will be freely available, published by our project team, but no one else will be able to publish them as their author's work.

2.4.3 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

They will be freely available, published by our project team, but no one else will be able to publish them as their author's work.

2.4.4 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

They will be visible and available for comparisons and application in practice, but not for publication by other persons. The scientific community will be able to refer to them by citing the publication itself.

2.4.5 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Data quality is related to the use of standardized methodology, diagnostic kits and methods that are standardized by the kit manufacturers themselves or by laboratory ISO and other standards.

3 Data security

3.1 Data security

3.1.1 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

The data will be located in the institution's repository, in case of data loss, they will be stored on my memory devices and can be deposited again in the repository itself.

3.1.2 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

They will be safe and secure for a long period of time.

4 Other research outputs

4.1 Making other research outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1 Will other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

They will refer to new carp breeding technology adapted to current climate challenges.

4.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

Yes, but they will be available in the publication and final report, which will address how this new technology is adapted to climate change and what is the most optimal way to apply additional aeration and different water column depths on production performance, health and stress in fish.

4.1.3 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Keywords will be set according to the keywords in the manuscript and will depend on the data itself.

4.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

The publication will show how the technology can be applied by other stakeholders.

4.2 Making other research outputs accessible

4.2.1 Repository

4.2.1.1 Will the other research outputs be deposited in a trusted repository?

It will be presented as part of a published paper that will be Open Access and available to everyone.

4.2.2 Other research outputs

4.2.2.1 Will all other research outputs be made openly available? If certain research outputs cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their research outputs closed if opening their research outputs goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

I will be openly available through Open Access publication.

4.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research outputs should be made available as soon as possible.

There is no embargo.

4.2.2.3 Will the other research outputs be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

It will be through Open Access publication.

4.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the other research outputs, both during and after the end of the project?

There is no restrictions on use.

4.2.2.5 How will the identity of the person accessing the other research outputs be ascertained?

There is no need to establish identity when it is Open Access.

4.2.3 Metadata

4.2.3.1 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the other research outputs?

No

Metadata about technology will be displayed in the published manuscript.

4.2.3.2 How long will the other research outputs remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after other research outputs is no longer available?

Permanently.

4.2.3.3 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the other research outputs be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

4.3 Making other research outputs interoperable

4.3.1 What other research outputs and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your other research outputs interoperable to allow other research outputs exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Research output as new technology will be interoperable for other disciplines and for manufacturers themselves because it allows for easy understanding and application of new technological improvements.

4.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

There is no need for mapping and special techniques.

4.4 Increase other research outputs re-use

4.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate other research outputs analysis and facilitate other research outputs re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, research outputs cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Units of measurement

The technology itself and its improvement derive from the parameters that are monitored and validated through the application of a standardized methodology.

4.4.2 Will your other research outputs be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your other research outputs be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

It will be freely available and published.

4.4.3 Will the other research outputs produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Technology is usable for the producers of fish.

4.4.5 Describe all relevant other research outputs quality assurance processes.

The quality of the technology itself and quality assurance are enabled through the application of adequate manufacturing practices that are implemented by applying the recommended aeration and fish pond depth, which has been implemented and verified through experiment testing.

4.4.6 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, research outputs security and ethical aspects.

This resource as a technology can be deployed and useful to fish producers and the scientific community dealing with this issue. The technology itself is safe and has no significant ethical challenges.

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Allocation of resources

5.1.1 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Direct cost

Other

The costs will be related to the publication of the Open Access publication.

5.1.2 How will these be covered?

They will be covered through our institutional funding for publication of papers.

5.1.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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5.1.4 How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Name of resource / activity	Description	Value	Currency
Data	Original data	No	
Technology	Open Access publication	3000	Euro

6 Ethics

6.1 Ethics

6.1.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics

review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No

There are no ethical challenges related to data sharing.

6.1.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No

7 Other issues

7.1 Other issues

7.1.1 Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Yes

I will use the University of Novi Sad repository, where I will deposit the original research data. This repository is available to all researchers employed in the University's institutions and there are no fees for its use.

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